

Investigation of Structural Systems in terms of the Decarbonizing Built Environment: Life Cycle Perspective

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Abstract

The construction industry is responsible for high energy consumption and environmental emissions. Building a decarbonized built environment requires evaluating the building industry in light of environmental performance criteria. In this respect, this study focuses on the environmental impact of structural elements, which constitute the largest percentage of a building. The study explains the life cycle assessment methodology and defines a life cycle framework for the analysis of structural systems. Life cycle energy and carbon analyses of alternative systems are performed using GaBi LCA software. The findings are evaluated in light of decarbonizing the built environment, and recommendations are presented. The study demonstrates the importance of the environmental impact of alternative systems, highlighting the necessity of incorporating environmental performance into an integrated decision-making mechanism at the early design stage.

Keywords: Life cycle assessment, built environment, decarbonization, structural systems.

Strüktür Sistemlerinin Yapılı Çevrenin Karbondan Arındırılması Açısından Araştırılması: Yaşam Döngüsü Perspektifi

Öz

Yapı endüstrisi yüksek enerji tüketimi ve çevresel emisyonlardan sorumludur. Karbondan arındırılmış bir yapı çevre inşa etmek yapı portföyünün performansının kriterlerini değerlendirmesini gerektirir. Bu açıdan bakıldığında, bir aktarımların en büyük yüzdesini taşıyan taşıyıcı sistem elemanlarının odağına odaklanılmaktadır. Çalışmada, yaşam problemleri değerlendirmesi sistematığı açıklanmakta ve yapısal sonuçlar analizi için yaşam dağılımı aralıkları sınıflandırılmaktadır. GaBi LCA yazılımı aracılığıyla alternatif sistemlerin yaşam sorunu enerji ve karbon analizleri gerçekleştirilmektedir. Yapılı çevrenin karbondan arındırılması elde edilen bulgular değerlendirilerek öneriler açıklanmaktadır. Çalışma, alternatif sistemlerin çevre üzerinde oluşturduğu etkinin önemini, gösteri performansının erken tasarım aşamasında bütünleşik bir karar sıcaklıklarına dahil edilememesinin gerekliliğini göstermektedir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Yaşam döngüsü değerlendirmesi, yapı çevre, dekarbonizasyon, strüktür sistemleri.

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1. Introduction

Today, many factors (rapid population growth, dense horizontal and vertical constructions, climate change, increase in motor vehicles, environmental pollution, and increased waste and residue, etc.) are progressively reducing the quality of life in cities. Thus, the ecosystem of cities is changing, and the balance between the functional and natural areas of the city is being disrupted (Gezer & Gül, 2009). It is scientifically established that the construction sector is responsible for approximately 40-50% of global greenhouse gas emissions, making a significant contribution to overall greenhouse gas emissions (Pittau et al., 2019). The built environment is associated with significant environmental impacts related to the construction and operation of buildings (Marinova et al., 2020). Green buildings, increasingly popular today, are defined as approaches that "reduce negative impacts on the climate and natural environment and create positive impacts throughout their entire life cycle." The aim of green buildings is to create a healthy environment for the future by using energy efficiently in buildings, utilizing backup energy sources, managing waste and residues (recycling support, reuse, etc.), managing water, and using sustainable materials (Gül et al., 2024). Environmental and social indicators of sustainable development draw attention to the construction industry. Creating an environmentally friendly building requires knowing the building's impact on the environment throughout its whole lifespan (Sharma et al., 2011).

Structural systems constitute the largest percentage of a building compared to other structural elements (Stek et al., 2011). Structural systems determine a building's response to seismic loads and influence the building's design, and consequently the amount of materials required (Agarwal & Shrikhande, 2006; European Commission, 2018). The structural system selection plays a vital role, as it forms the building's framework and requires significant resources (Bhuiyan et al., 2023). Therefore, understanding and analyzing the environmental impacts of structural systems throughout their lifecycle is of great importance.

Lifecycle assessment (LCA), as a crucial tool for environmental management, is an internationally accepted criterion. LCA can be defined as the calculation and evaluation of the inputs, outputs, and potential environmental impacts of a product or system throughout its lifecycle (Zuo et al., 2017). The LCA approach evaluates different scenarios and possibilities to minimize energy and resource consumption and reduce the environmental footprint of building materials (Oladazimi et al., 2020).

Environmental impact is primarily related to resource use and greenhouse gas emissions. In this respect, energy use and carbon emissions are commonly used measures of the environmental impact of buildings (Fay & Treloar, 2003;). LCA is an objective process aimed at identifying and quantifying the environmental burdens, energy and material uses, and emissions associated with a product, process, or activity, as well as assessing and implementing opportunities to impact environmental improvements. Given that the built environment is responsible for a very large percentage of global annual CO₂ emissions from energy sources, the construction sector presents a significant opportunity to lead transformative change and has the strongest potential among all industrial sectors, offering opportunities to adopt sustainability practices and enhance resilience (Calle Müller et al., 2024). Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a comprehensive and systematically powerful approach to environmental assessment, and its inclusion in decision-making processes for the selection of building elements or components is of great importance (Cabeza et al., 2014). Decarbonizing the construction industry and transitioning to a more sustainable building environment requires all stakeholders to understand the environmental impact of materials and processes throughout the entire lifecycle of infrastructure.

The literature shows that the issue of load-bearing system performance is often reduced to a single performance criterion, such as seismic performance or static effect (Guerrero et al., 2023; Simonen et al., 2015). In studies focusing on comparative life cycle analysis of alternative building systems, life cycle analyses are performed implicitly (Kim et al., 2013; Oladazimi et al., 2020; Balasbaneh & Ramli, 2020). Analyzing and evaluating structural systems, which constitute the largest percentage of a building compared to other building elements, in terms of environmental performance criteria, is critical for achieving a carbon-neutral built environment. Structural system evaluation criteria are not limited to static performance; they must also be considered in light of environmental performance.

The efficiency of alternative load-bearing systems can be analyzed using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), a robust performance evaluation criterion. Steel and reinforced concrete are structural frames with a high usage area in the world (Oladazimi et al., 2020). In this respect, examining the environmental impacts of these frames has become a necessity. In this regard, steel and reinforced concrete load-bearing systems constitute the scope of this study. This study aims to investigate the environmental impacts of structural systems and demonstrate the importance of incorporating sustainable building component alternatives into the decision-making process during the early design phase. A framework is presented for this purpose. The aim is to highlight the importance of evaluating alternative systems in light of their life cycles for decarbonizing the built environment.

2. Material and Method

This study first explains the life cycle systematic and defines and describes a life cycle assessment framework for structural systems. Within this framework, life cycle analyses of steel and reinforced concrete structural system alternatives under the same conditions are performed using GaBi LCA software. GaBi is an LCA software and tool designed to reduce carbon and other environmental emissions and contribute to sustainability. It is a tool that enables environmentally friendly decision-making by analyzing the entire life cycle of a product, from raw material extraction to disposal (Sphera, n.d.). The assessments are explained in light of the data obtained in the context of decarbonizing the built environment. Residential buildings constitute 86% of all buildings in Türkiye (Somer, 2025). According to Turkish Statistical Institute (TUIK) data for 2024/2025, the total number of residential buildings in Türkiye is 2.3 million (TUIK, n.d.). In this context, the focus of this study is on residential buildings.

3. Findings and Discussion

This section first explains the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology and defines the LCA framework for structural systems. Based on this defined LCA framework, steel and reinforced concrete structural frames are analyzed, and the findings are evaluated.

3.1. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) Systematic

As an important tool in environmental management, life cycle assessment is an internationally accepted standard. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) can be defined as the calculation and evaluation of the inputs, outputs, and potential environmental impacts of a product system throughout its life cycle (Zuo et al., 2017). The definition and general method of Life Cycle Assessment are described in the ISO 14044: 2006 (International Organization for Standardization, 2006) LCA Guidelines and Requirements standard, and the four basic stages are as follows: Purpose and Scope Definition, Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), and Interpretation.

The Purpose and Scope Definition refers to defining and describing the product, system, or process, the purpose of the study, the functional unit, the system boundaries, the impact assessment method, the impact categories, the assumptions, the limitations, etc. Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) Analysis includes collecting data related to raw materials, energy consumption, emissions, waste, etc., to measure the inputs and outputs of the life cycle phase. The collection and organization of data to be used in the defined LCA study. It is an inventory of the input/output data related to the system being studied. Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) is the evaluation of potential environmental impacts. This stage includes the selection of impact categories and category indicators, and the allocation of inventory data to the selected impact categories. Interpretation means analyzing the results based on LCI and LCIA, extracting the main findings, limitations, and possible recommendations (Chau et al., 2015).

Life Cycle Assessment Principles and System Boundaries are shown in Figure 1. Environmental load occurs at each stage of the life cycle and according to the sub-parameters that constitute these stages. Energy consumption and emissions occur in each module. In the life cycle systematic, energy and carbon exist in embodied and operational forms. Operational energy or carbon refers to the energy consumption and carbon emissions required for heating, cooling, ventilation, and air conditioning a building. Embodied energy and embodied carbon refer to the energy consumed and environmental emissions produced during material production, building construction, building maintenance & repair

processes, and end-of-life processes. Embodied energy is the sum of initial, recurring, and decommissioned embodied energies. Initial energy is the total energy used to extract raw materials, produce and transport products and components, and construct a building. Recurring energy is the energy required to maintain the building while it is in use. Demolition energy is the energy consumed to dismantle a building at the end of its life cycle, recycling and reusing some components and disposing of others by transporting waste to landfills or incineration plants (Azari & Abbasabadi, 2018). Life Cycle Assessment Principles and System Boundaries are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Life Cycle Assessment Principles and System Boundaries (European Committee for Standardization, 2011)

In the study, the life cycle framework includes the product manufacturing module, the construction module, the end-of-life module, and the recovery module. It does not consider the use phase (B1-B7). In terms of operational loads, structural systems do not directly affect the operational energy and carbon loads of a building, such as heating, cooling, ventilation, and air conditioning. In terms of embodied loads, repair, demolition, or reuse of a load-bearing system requires static or seismic performance analysis. Furthermore, international standards define the life of a load-bearing system as one hundred (100) years, and in the life cycle approach, the life is generally considered to be fifty (50) years. The International Energy Agency (IEA) states in its ANNEX 57 (IEA ANNEX 57, 2016) that scenarios should be planned for the maintenance, repair, and reuse of structural systems. The LCA framework for structural systems is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Life cycle assessment framework for structural systems (Created by the authors)

3.2. The Case Study Based on the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

In this study, steel and reinforced concrete structural frames are analyzed in terms of life cycle embodied energy and embodied carbon. To measure the efficiency of alternative systems, these systems must be under the same conditions. In this respect, two alternative structural systems are accepted at the Earthquake Ground Motion Level-4. The analyzed structure has a central core plan typology. In this study, the structural frame, shear wall core, and floor slab constitute the load-bearing system components. Alternative load-bearing systems with defined properties are modeled in GaBi LCA software, and LCA analyses are performed. Information regarding structural systems is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Properties of steel and reinforced concrete structural framed buildings

Properties	Steel Structure	Reinforced Concrete Structure
Soil Class	ZA (Solid)	ZA (Solid)
Building Type	Residential Building	Residential Building
Building Lifespan	50 years	50 years
Total Gross Residence Area	600 m ²	600 m ²
Number of Floors and Height	8 Story and 24 m	8 Story and 24 m
Structural Frame Type	Steel Structural Frame	Reinforced Concrete Structural Frame
Column Dimension (cm)	HEB 300	40x40
Beam Dimension (cm)	IPE 500	40x50
Flooring Type	Composite Flooring	R.C. Slab
Flooring Height (cm)	12 cm	18 cm
Core Type	Steel Core	R.C. Core
Core Dimension (cm)	330x560 cm	330x560 cm
Total Concrete	1.440 t	3.210 t
Total Rebar	20 t	33 t
Total Structural Steel	175 t	-
Total Steel Connection Elements	300 kg	-
Total Trapezoidal Sheet Amount	38 t	-

The steel and reinforced concrete structural systems modeled in the GaBi software are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. a. Reinforced concrete structural system in GaBi, **b.** Steel structural system in GaBi (Created by the authors using GaBi software)

The total amount of embodied energy of the steel load-bearing system is 5.03E006 (5.03×10^6) MJ, and embodied carbon is 3.42E006 (3.42×10^6) kgCO₂eq. The total amount of embodied energy of the reinforced concrete load-bearing system is 6.16E006 (6.16×10^6) MJ, and embodied carbon is 1.91E006 (1.91×10^6) kgCO₂eq. The embodied energy and embodied carbon values of steel and reinforced concrete structural systems are shown in the graph (Figure 4).

Figure 4. LCA Results for steel and reinforced concrete structural systems (Created by the authors)

According to LCA results, steel is advantageous in terms of carbon emissions, while reinforced concrete is advantageous in terms of energy consumption. Studies in the literature also present environmental indicators that demonstrate high or low performance for steel and reinforced concrete structural systems (Guggemos & Horvath, 2005; Kim et al., 2013; Oladazimi et al., 2020). From this perspective, it is difficult to comment on the efficiency of alternative structural systems. At this point, it should be noted that for a decision-making mechanism, the analyses should be evaluated considering parameters such as the system framework and local characteristics.

4. Conclusion and Suggestions

A large portion of the materials extracted and consumed worldwide are related to the construction sector, and this volume is expected to increase significantly, particularly due to the projected growth of the global housing stock. Studies in the field of static or seismic performance of alternative building systems are extensive, but these studies often reduce the issue of performance-based design to a single performance aspect, such as static impact. There are many parameters to consider when evaluating the performance of alternative building systems, and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is the most powerful performance assessment approach.

In line with the goal of a carbon-neutral built environment, careful evaluation of structural systems, which constitute the largest percentage of a building, is necessary. In this respect, this study comprehensively presents the literature in the context of decarbonizing the built environment and conducts life cycle analyses of alternative structural systems. The findings show a strong relationship between structural systems and life cycle carbon emissions. In addition, it should be stated that integrated systems are needed to evaluate the environmental performance of alternative structural systems. Further transformations towards sustainability in the built environment can be achieved through a low-carbon building stock and reduced emissions; This requires the evaluation and optimization of buildings and materials. Especially for countries like Türkiye, which have a very high building stock that needs renovation, an environmentally performance-oriented approach is a solution to environmental problems.

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Author Contribution and Conflict of Interest Disclosure Information

All authors contributed equally to the article. There is no conflict of interest.

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